

STUDY ON FIBER ORIENTATION AND LOW CYCLE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF POLYMER INJECTION WELDS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the microstructure related polymer injection welds and low cycle fatigue behavior of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics. The microstructure of an injection molded weld was studied by microscopic methods for the purpose of describing the fiber orientation. Injection welds are the place where two flow fronts come together, leading to fiber orientations having flower and volcano-like patterns. The polymer composite materials used in the experiment were polycarbonate(PC) with amorphous structure containing 30% short glass fiber and polyphenylene sulfide(PPS) with crystalline structure included 40% short glass fiber. The specimen used was a compact type specimen with a parent and weld line created by double gate injection molding. Low cycle fatigue test was carried out and measured the fatigue crack length using the clip gage, Krak gage and optical method. Microtoming technique was used for slicing ultrathin sections from the molded polymer parts. Microstructural analysis of fiber orientation was carried out using light transmission microscopy(LM) and scanning electronic microscopy(SEM). Fatigue crack growth rate was dependent on the fiber orientation at parent and weld line..

Key words : Short glass fiber filled polymer, Low cycle fatigue, Fiber orientation, Microtoming technique, Polymer injection weld, Flower-like pattern.

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic injection moldings form the weld line because of the presence of cores, pin, corners

and multiple gates that divide the polymer melt during flow in the mold. This is a weld region where two flow fronts come together. Formation of weld line in injection molded products is practically unavoidable[1-3]. An understanding of the fracture behavior of polymer composite materials subjected to constant and cyclic loading is necessary for predicting the life time of structures fabricated with polymers. The fatigue behavior of thermoplastics has assumed increasing importance in recent years as these materials have become more widely used in load bearing applications. There is thus a need to acquire a better understanding of the fatigue performance and failure mechanisms of these materials under such conditions.

An important class of short-fiber composites is the recently developed sheet molding compound, which is currently used in many engineering applications such as automobile structures and components[4,5]. In general, these components and structures are subjected to repeated loading during service. Fatigue failure of the composites is, therefore, a subject of major concern in design[6] and cyclic crack propagation is of particular significance in the fatigue life prediction of short fiber sheet molding compound composites. Riddell, et al. [7] and Pabiot[8] investigated the fatigue failure mechanism in thermoplastics. They found that thermoplastics generally fail by drastic increase in temperature due to the damping capacity of the material.

Therefore, in this study, the analysis of fiber orientation and the fatigue crack growth behaviors at weld line and the bulk without weld line have been studied by low cycle fatigue test, SEM, image analyzer and light-transmission microscope(LM) for observing the ultrathin sections.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The polymer composite materials used in this experiment are polycarbonate (PC) with amorphous structure representing a general engineering plastics included 30% short glass fiber and polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) with crystalline structure having 40% short glass fiber content. The diameter of the glass fiber is 13 μ m and its length is 200~400 μ m. A double-gated mold was used in this study for injection molding with a parent and weld line. Four kinds of CT specimen, PP, PT, WP and WT as shown in Figure 1 was machined from injection plate for fatigue test. The mold conditions are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 ; Injection molding conditions

	G. F Fraction (wt%)	Injection Temp. (°C)	Mold Temp. (°C)
PC (G 2530)	30	320	115
PPS (C-1000SG)	40	320	135

Fig. 1 ; Layout and dimensions of injection mold and specimens

Microtoming techniques[9] for slicing ultrathin sections from molded polymer parent and weld parts, coupled with LM, are emerging as important procedures for making an accurate microstructural analysis of fiber orientation within an injection-molded part.

This kind of approach can provide the molder with information for failure analysis, part and mold design, and especially analysis of flow direction and processing optimization.. These sliced sections should be polished as thin as possible to achieve maximum clarity for the microscopic analysis of fiber orientation of polymer injection weld parts. In this study specimens have been microtomed and polished consecutively with #200,#400 and #800 powders with a polisher, they are then polished by hand with #2000 and #3000 alumina powder on a glass plate. The resulting sections are about 10~15 microns thick, and ready for microscopic observation.

For the visualization of fiber orientation, two different methods may be used: LM and SEM. To ensure better contrasting of glass fibers, the LM-technique was proposed recently[10]. Fiber orientations of PC and PPS in the parent and weld material were observed by LM with the ultrathin 10~15µm sections. Also, the fracture surfaces of the specimens were observed by SEM at an accelerating voltage of 10kV.

Constant amplitude tests were obtained with load ratios, $R=P_{min}/P_{max}$, of approximately 0.1 and using a positive haversine wave with frequencies 0.017-1.67 as shown in Table 2.

All tests were terminated when the crack growth rate became too great to accurately measure the crack length or when the uncracked ligament of the specimen (w-a) ceased to be predominately elastic. Crack

length, a, versus applied cycles, N, data reduced to da/dN versus delta K using a second order incremental polynomial method for constant amplitude tests.

Table 2 ; Fatigue test condition

		Parent		Weld	
		Transverse	Parallel	Transverse	Parallel
PC	Pmax (N)	400	400	255	255
	Pmin (N)	40	40	40	40
	Frequency (Hz)	0.038	0.028	0.018	0.017
PPS	Pmax (N)	550	400	400	400
	Pmin (N)	50	40	50	40
	Frequency (Hz)	1.67	1.67	1.67	1.67

3. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure of parent and weld metal

The fiber orientation pattern is highly influenced by mold geometry, processing conditions and rheological properties of the material. The rheological properties are affected by the viscosity and by other factors such as fiber aspect ratio, injection temperature and pressure.

As shown in Figures. 2 and 3, a detailed characterization of the fiber morphology of injection flow was obtained by means of LM from sheets at orientation parallel and perpendicular to the injection flow direction. Reinforcement such as glass fibers do show preferred orientations. To obtain maximum use of the glass fiber, they must flow into the part in the proper direction to solidify in the preferred orientation. When examining for flow and orientation, it is necessary to microtome the specimen parallel to the direction of flow. Figure.2 (a,b) shows the picture of the PC parent with perpendicular and parallel orientations of glass fiber, relative to the injection flow direction, respectively. The orientation of short glass fiber is nearly the same direction as the injection flow, so shows the section area of glass fiber to perpendicular direction. Figure 3 (a,b) also show the picture of the PPS parent. They have nearly the same orientation of glass fiber as the PC, but parallel direction of PPS parent is some random of glass fiber compared with PC parent.

(a) perpendicular direction.

(b) parallel direction.

(a) perpendicular direction.

(b) parallel direction.

Fig. 2 ; Photomicrographs taken on fiber orientation of PC parent

Fig. 3 ; Photomicrograph taken on fiber orientation of PPS parent

Figure.4 shows photomicrographs taken of fiber orientation in the PC weld in x-z plane. The fiber orientation in the weld line is perpendicular to the mold filled direction(MFD), that is, nearly the direction of x-y plane. The flow front is of the spherical type during injection, due to melt freezing effects in the direct vicinity of the mold surface. When two flow is encountered at one point due to difference in the flow front profile during cavity filling, fibers of flow front change to perpendicular direction and next coming fiber inject to the degree of 45° nearly, so side part of mold surface shows the flower type. So we called the apperence of fiber pattern at weld parts the flower-like pattern[11]. Figure 5 is the microstructure of PC weld showing glass fiber flow. Flow of two direction come together at one point and makes a weld region. It shows the volcano-like mechanism[12] which creates orientation at 90 angles to main polymer flow direction, comparing to flow-like pattern

Fig. 4 ; Photomicrograph of flower-like pattern of PC weld in the x-z plane

Fig. 5 ; Photomicrograph of volcano-like pattern of PC weld in the y-z plane

created at the wide area. At that time, as shown in Table 1, the temperature of melt is higher than that of mold, so mold cool down the melt and increase its viscosity at the edges of the channel thus retarding the flow. Flow at the center of channel continues at higher rates creating melt spill from center to edges of channel.

Figure 6 shows the result of fiber orientation analysis of the PPS weld by Image Analyzer. The "a" position has the glass fiber at 90° to the MFD. Here the two flow fronts are recombining and changing the fiber orientation. of two flow fronts. In the "b" position, most of the glass fiber is at 45°, while the orientation within the "c" position, middle of flow, is mostly 45° and 135°. At (d) the glass fibers are predominantly at 0° and 180° orientations, i.e., parallel to the MFD.

Fig. 6 ; Orientation analysis of glass fiber by Image Analyzer

3.2 Fatigue crack growth behaviors and Fractography

Figure 7 show the relation between crack length, a, and applied cycles, N, at PC parent. In this figure, the results of clip gage and optical method are nearly same but that of Krak gage is slightly high. Fatigue crack growth rate, da/dN versus delta K curves for four material conditions of PC by Krak gage are shown in Figure 8. The results of PP and WP make no difference, but fatigue crack growth rate, da/dN increase again after decreasing in spite of increment of delta K from weld line of WT changing the fiber orientation. PC and PPS that weld line is perpendicular to the direction of crack growth have the turnover area at the da/dN-delta K curves. There are some reports about the turnover result [13,14]. In considering the fiber orientation and fiber volume fraction, Young modulus near the weld line of WT is assumed to the reason of crack growth and closure behaviors. The da/dN of PT oriented perpendicular to direction of crack growth slowly increase compare to the others.

Fig. 7 ; Fatigue crack growth curve for the PC parent

Fig. 8 ; Fatigue crack growth rate versus delta K for each material conditions of PC

Figure 9 shows the crack length, a, versus applied fatigue cycles, N, of the four PPS materials and Figure 10 is the curves of delta K- da/dN. In this figure, PP, PT and WP are changing smoothly, but

WT is changing on the way samely PC specimen. The change of crack length versus applied cycles at the last part of WT is shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 9 ; Fatigue crack growth curve for each material conditions of PPS

Fig. 10 ; Fatigue crack growth rate versus delta K for each material conditions of PPS

3.3 SEM observation of fracture surface

Figure 12 (a, b) show the fracture surface of PP and PT after fatigue test. Fiber orientation of partial surface and central area is perpendicular to the direction of cracking growth and 75% of the fracture surface area is parallel in the PP material. But PT has the fiber orientation paralleled to the direction of crack growth in the central area and the rest of fracture surface is perpendicular to the crack growth and about 80%.

Fig. 11 ; Crack length - applied cycle curve at the last part of weld

Fig. 12 (a) (b) ; SEM fractography of PPS parent

4. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions derived from the experimental results on the microstructural characteristics and fatigue crack growth behaviors of PC and PPS injection weld are summarized as follows:

1. Microstructure and fiber orientation of PC and PPS injection flow is dependent on the position within the mold, especially at injection welds, where two flow fronts come together creating flower and volcano-like patterns of fiber orientation.
2. Fatigue strength of PP having fiber parallel to the direction of crack growth is the lowest among the four kind of materials.
3. Fatigue crack growth behaviors of WT and PP are nearly same, but the crack growth behaviors around the weld line once delay and is the same to PT in the last parts.

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